

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW PROCESSES FOR AEROSPACE STRUCTURAL COMPOSITE PART MANUFACTURING WITH AFFORDABLE COST AND HIGH RAMP UP CAPABILITY WITHIN EFFICOMP PROJECT.

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Abstract

For next civil aircraft generation, the schedule is to produce 60 aircrafts per month. Today, large size parts production with conventional processes such as autoclave curing allows the production of about 1 part per day. To fulfill 60 aircrafts per month the number of autoclave to invest will be too high to comply with global final production cost.

This paper presents results on new processes development done during EFFICOMP project to reduce the cost and the manufacturing time of structural thermoset composite parts.

Composite panels up to 80 plies have been cured with a new concept of resistive curing based on Joule effect in carbon fibres with a heating rate of 10°C/min.

Composite thin panels with curvature representative of fuselage panels have been successfully laid-down with automated deposition of semi cured tows, and final polymerization done out of autoclave in a simple oven.

The Latest results are moreover highlighted.

Conclusions are drawn, which address the robustness and reliability of these new technologies, with regards to the final quality of the composite parts.

Keywords : Resistive curing; Joule effect; Automated Fibers Deposition; Carbon Fibers Reinforced Composites; Semi-Cure Process.

1. Introduction

This paper presents results obtained in the H2020 funded project EFFICOMP. Two main topics are addressed in this presentation. The first one is the development of a new concept to cure composite that we call resistive curing [1], the second one is the development of a new technology based on semi cured tows laid down automatically, with a final out of autoclave post cure [2], [3]. These two topics have the same final objective, reduce manufacturing cost of composite structural parts and increase production rate to fulfill future objective to produce more than 60 aircraft per month.

2. Resistive curing

With this new concept we heat directly the composite material by introducing electrical current inside the carbon fibre and then increase the temperature of the composite by the Joule effect. The temperature is controlled by the electrical power introduced in the composite (Figure 1). Some work has been published on this concept by heating the mould [4], or directly the fibre of the composite [5], [6].

The mains advantages of this concept are :

- Curing time reduction. Objective of a factor 2 reduction on global curing time compare to conventional autoclave process by changing heating rate from 0.5°C/min to 10 °C/min.
- Possibility of high heating rate with limited inertia compared to conventional heating with heat conduction in the composite from the laminate surface to the centre of the laminate.
- Energy consumption reduction. No need to heat all autoclave and tool, but only the composite.
- Limitation of temperature difference between hot and cold area in the composite during the curing cycle

The prepreg material used to perform the tests was a UD tape prepreg with 194 g/m² of dry fibre and 34% by weight of epoxy resin.

Figure 1 : Principle used to cure composite with current introduction in carbon fibre and Joule effect to heat the composite.

2.1. Tests on dry fibres

The evolution of carbon fibre electrical conductivity versus temperature evolution has been determined by measuring the resistance of a 3K high resistance carbon fibre with 4 probes methodology in a temperature regulated oven. The obtained results are presented Figure 2. The measured resistance decrease with the increase of temperature. This is the typical evolution of a semi conductive material. With conductive material the resistance increases with temperature increase.

Figure 2 : Evolution of carbon fibre resistance versus temperature.

2.2. Tests on 6 plies UD laminate.

First test have been done on a laminate made from 6 plies UD tape with a size of 280x200 mm as presented Figure 3. The curing cycle applied was 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate of 10°C/min. The temperature measurement on the surface of the laminate was done by thermocouples and with infra-red camera as presented Figure 4.

We clearly see on Figure 4 that the more distance we have from current introduction, the highest resistance we have in the electrical circuit and the lowest is the measured temperature. This is a first important result to take in consideration.

Through the length of the sample (280 mm) the temperature is very homogeneous as we can see Figure 5.

Figure 3 : Test done on 6 plies UD tape prepreg

Figure 4 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 6 plies UD tape laminate. Temperature distribution through the width of the laminate

Figure 5 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 6 plies UD tape laminate. Temperature distribution through the length of the laminate

2.3. Tests on 6 plies UD laminate with symmetric current introduction.

To obtain a more homogeneous temperature through the width of laminate we modified the current introduction with a more symmetric way as presented Figure 6. The curing cycle applied was 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate of 10°C/min.

Figure 6 : Test done on 6 plies UD tape prepreg with symmetric current introduction through steel plates.

The measured temperature through the width of the sample with the infra-red camera is much more homogeneous as we can see Figure 7. The measured temperature through the thickness is very homogeneous as we can also see Figure 7. The temperature is also very homogeneous through the length of the laminate as we can see Figure 8.

Figure 7 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 6 plies UD tape laminate. Temperature distribution through the thickness of the laminate

Figure 8 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 6 plies UD tape laminate. Temperature distribution through the length of the laminate.

2.4. Tests on 7 plies UD laminate with symmetric current introduction perpendicular to the fibre direction.

We also verify the efficiency of this curing technology on UD samples with current introduction perpendicular to the fibre direction as presented Figure 9.

Figure 9 : Test done on 7 plies UD tape prepreg with current introduction through copper plates perpendicular to the fibre direction.

The results are presented Figure 10. The measured temperature on the surface of the laminate with the infra-red camera is very homogeneous, but we can not heat the composite at the desired temperature. We can not go other 85°C after two hours with an imposed temperature of 180°C.

Figure 10 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 7 plies UD tape laminate. Current introduction perpendicular to the fibre direction.

2.5. Tests on 8 plies QI lay up laminate with symmetric current introduction.

We performed a test on quasi isotropic laminate of 8 plies as presented Figure 11.

Figure 11 : Test done on 8 plies QI lay up tape prepreg with current introduction through copper plates

Measured temperatures through the thickness of the laminate are presented Figure 12. We observed a very good homogeneity of temperature through the thickness of the composite.

Measured temperatures through the diagonal on the surface of the laminate are presented Figure 13. We observed a very good homogeneity of the temperature except close to the edges of the laminate due to thermal exchange with the outside from the edges.

Figure 12 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 8 plies QI lay up laminate. Temperature distribution through the thickness of the laminate.

Good temperature homogeneity through the laminate (points 5, 10, 11, 12 and 13)

Temperature reduction at the edges due to thermal exchange on the edges (points 1, 9 and 3, 7)

Figure 13 : Curing test 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 8 plies QI lay up laminate. Temperature distribution through the diagonal of the laminate.

2.6. Tests on 80 plies QI lay up laminate with symmetric current introduction.

We performed a test on quasi isotropic laminate of 80 plies as presented Figure 14. The thickness of the laminate was about 15 mm. We also added an insulating layer on the edges of the laminate.

Figure 14 : Test done on 80 plies QI lay up tape prepreg with current introduction through copper plates.

Measured temperatures through the thickness of the laminate are presented Figure 15 and Figure 16. On Figure 15 during the heating rate we have a limited temperature overshoot of about 15°C at the 150°C dwell and of about 5°C at the 180°C dwell. This is a very good result if we consider the thickness of the thickness of the composite (15 mm) and the heating rate applied (10°C/min). Figure 16, we observed a very good homogeneity of temperature through the thickness of the composite at the stabilized state on both dwells 150°C and 180°C.

Figure 15 : Curing test 3 hours at 150°C + 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 80 plies QI lay up laminate. Temperature distribution through the thickness of the laminate during the curing cycle.

Figure 16 : Curing test 3 hours at 150°C + 2 hours at 180°C with heating rate 10 °C/min on 80 plies QI lay up laminate. Temperature distribution through the thickness of the laminate at the stabilized state on the two dwells.

3. Semi-curing

The stakes of Airbus CTO is to develop a specific composites technology, which is based on automated deposition of semi cured tows, associated with Out of Autoclave post cure of the AFP parts.

The applications which are targeted are on a general point of view manufacturing of structural Carbon Fibres Reinforced panels, and especially primary parts such as Fuselage skins, wing covers, Box panels etc...

The main benefits of the targeted process are:

- To avoid AFP machines cleaning, because of the use of pre-cured material.
- To avoid cooling system in the AFP machine (no chemical evolution of the material (tow))
- Material extended shop-life.
- Room temperature storage and transportation.(no need of freezers)
- Final Parts thickness reached without compaction steps.
- Investments cost limitation (no need of autoclave)

Therefore It is hoped that combination of lay down process automation with pre-cured tows with Out of Autoclave post cure will lead to important recurrent and non-recurrent production costs, and production times.

To note also that Airbus Group has patented this specific AFP process with use of semi-cured tapes (see references [2] and [3])

3.1. Automated Fibres Placement of Semi Cured Thermoset Composite Tows.

The Material which has been supplied by TORAY for completion of the Airbus CTO R&D works, is a thermoset Carbon Fibres Reinforced tape.

- TORAY **T800S/3911 UD-tape**, FAW **268g/sqm**, Rc **34%**.
- Roll definitions: Width = 1 200 mm, Length = 45 m.

The targeted part for support of the development is a curved panel, as shown into the following Figure 17, with previous TP applications: the dimensions are 300mm * 600 mm and the curvatures are roughly representative of fuselage panels.

Different Thicknesses (from 2 to 10 mm) were aimed to be investigated in order to explore the field of application of the technology.

Figure 17 : curved panel demonstrator & Airbus Group AFP machine

The development plan assumed to investigate the influence of the degree of cure of the tows for AFP, the influence of the AFP process parameters (speed, Heat Power, Pressure) and at last to try to evaluate the capabilities for such kind of pre-cured panels, to be Out Of Autoclave post cured.

3.2. Preliminary works.

Physico chemical tests, i.e DSC (see Figure 18) and Rheological tests, have been first of all performed, in order to build a Material & Process windows, and to determine the adapted pre-cure cycles, which could lead to the targeted degrees of pre-cure.

Figure 18 : dynamic and isothermal + residual DSC tests.

From these analysis, AGI was able to determine the pre-cure cycles to use for manufacture semi-cured tows.

The process is the following :

- Pre-cure the large width TORAY rolls at 2 different degrees of cure (20% and 30% targeted) and at a low temperatures.
- Slitting of these” semi cured” rolls into 6.35 mm (1/4 inch) width tows.

These pre-cured tows have been installed in the Airbus Group AFP machine (named FLASH TP) for **automated deposition** of the different 3911/T800S plies.

Figure 19 : Semi cured tows on AFP machine with different polymerization ratio.

As observed on the previous images, some deposition problems occurred due to:

- The nature of the tape, which is an heavy grade: it induced important memory shape effects.
- The “poor-medium” quality of the slit tows, with presence of fibrils, powder, and bad quality of tows edge (internal tow slitting could occur during deposition).

3.3. Automated Fibres deposition with semi cured tows.

Semi-cured curved panels have been manufactured with the AGI AFP Machine, and automated deposition of 8 pre-cured tows. .

- 20% polymerization ratio tows: 8 plies thick QI panels + 40 plies thick QI panel.
 - The lay down parameters are:
 - 8 plies panel : $v= 0.04$ mm/sec, $P = 100$ W & $P = 750$ W.
 - 40 plies panel : $v= 0.04$ mm/sec, $P = 1000$ W
- 30% polymerization ratio tows: 8 plies thick QI panels + 16 plies thick QI panel
 - The lay down parameters are
 - 8 plies thick panels:
 - $v= 0.1$ mm/sec, $P = 2000$ W.
 - $v= 0.03$ mm/sec, $P = 600$ W.
 - 16 plies thick panel:
 - $v= 0.03$ mm/sec, $P = 600$ W.

Figure 20 : automated fibres placement of curved panels with 30% polymerization ratio tows

The here-above pictures are showing the three 30% pre-cured panels just after the AFP phase.

The average measured thicknesses did not point any differences between the 3 panels:

- 8 plies panels: 0.260 mm/ply & 0.261 mm/ply
- 40 plies panel: 0.261 mm/ply

The average measured thicknesses showed a certain impact of the velocity speed on the part quality:

- 8 plies panels: 0.259 mm/ply & 0.253 mm/ply.
- 16 plies panel: 0.261 mm/ply.

It remains nevertheless that the results are quite similar to the post cure targets, with regards to tape grade, whatever the degrees of pre-polymerization of the tows are.

3.4. Post cure of AFP semi-cured panels in oven.

All the panels have been post cured under (max) vacuum only, with a final temperature dwell at 180 °C during 150 min, in order to reach a minimum degree of polymerization. We aimed to insure high levels enough of thermo-mechanical properties, related to the targets of Manufacture of structural (class I) aeronautical composites Parts.

Figure 21 : Post cure of 20% polymerization ratio panels

Figure 22 : Post cured panels

To note that the thicknesses after post cure are quite similar to the just laydown panels, which demonstrate the interest of the semi-cure technology.

3.5. Quality expertise.

NDT analysis (C-SCAN at 5 Mhz) have been made in double transmission mode, according to the AITM norm, on post cured 20% precured panels (see Figure 23).

Identical quality of 8 plies thick parts has been observed, because quite the same attenuation and homogenous time of flights

Even if important structural noise has been noticed on the CSCAN cartography of the thicker panel , and also some (associated) thickness variation (undulations presence ?), it seems quite acceptable, with regards to the global attenuation level (< -6 DB).

Figure 23 : C-SCAN cartographies of the 8 plies thick 20% polymerization ratio panels.

Micrographs have been made from extracted coupons in the centre of the panels presented Figure 24 and Figure 25.

Figure 24 : post cured panels from 20% pre-cured blankets

Figure 25 : post cured panels from 30% pre-cured blankets

Although measured thicknesses trended to indicate a quite good health of the parts, a presence of micro-porosities has been detected in any case, at the inter-ply level for the biggest ones, and at the intra-ply level.

The induced pressure by vacuum during the post cure was not sufficient to forbid void growth or to collapse pre-existing defects (due to poor quality of tows) into semi cured AFP blankets: the use of an heavy grade material seems also not to be the optimized material solution, for vacuum consolidation process, even if it could be interesting on a cost effective point of view.

4. Conclusion

Resistive curing.

The new developed concept of resistive curing gives first very promising results. Heating rates of 10°C/min can be achieved without any problem to decrease significantly global curing cycle time. Temperature of the laminate surface is quit homogeneous except at the edges proximity with temperatures reduction. A laminate with 80 plies have been successfully cured with heating rate of 10°C/min and homogeneous temperature through the thickness of the laminate.

Automate deposition of semi-cured tows + OOA post cure

CFRC Panels with fuselage representative curvatures have been successfully lay-down with automated deposition of semi-cured tows. Some difficulties have been encountered, even if the blanket compaction levels, just after fibres deposition, is quite equivalent to this one of fully cured parts. OOA post cures have been completed and expertise analysis has shown a small remaining presence of porosities into panels. The influence of the material quality, more than the process itself, is highlighted, such as the heavy tape grade and the slit tows health.

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